

shows the inherent behavior of modulus
decreasing and then increasing with increasing strain.
3.166
The phenomenon is possible but no good explanation was
given

ON THE MODULUS OF KFRP LAMINATES IN STATIC AND FATIGUE LOADING

H.L.Ganczakowski, P.A.Smith* & P.W.R.Beaumont.
Cambridge University Engineering Department,
Trumpington Street,
Cambridge. CB2 1PZ.
England.

* Department of Materials Science and Engineering,
University of Surrey,
Guildford. GU2 5XH.
England.

ABSTRACT

The behaviour of unidirectional and cross-ply Kevlar fibre reinforced plastic (KFRP) laminates has been studied under static and fatigue loading. The stiffness of unidirectional laminates has been shown to increase under static loading and with fatigue cycling, although on unloading it may subsequently return to its original value. For cross-ply laminates, a decrease in stiffness under static loading has been found, due to matrix cracking in the transverse plies. Under fatigue loading, the stiffness changes of the cross-ply laminate have been found to be complicated by the stiffening of the unidirectional layers. ('Kevlar' is a trade name of the Du Pont Company.)

INTRODUCTION

The initial damage observed in fibre-reinforced composite materials under load is generally matrix cracking in the off-axis plies. It may result in long-term property degradation and in some cases the cracks that appear in the material may render it useless for its intended application, (pressure vessels, for example).

Transverse ply cracking has been observed under static loading in both glass- and carbon-fibre reinforced polymers (GFRP and CFRP), e.g.[1-3], and a similar pattern of cracks has been recorded in fatigue, leading to the proposal of a 'characteristic damage state', independent of variables such as load history and environment, e.g.[4-5]. Various theories have been proposed [6-13] to try to model the development of matrix cracking under static and fatigue loading, and these show promise when compared with the available experimental data for GFRP and CFRP. To our knowledge, there are no detailed studies of matrix cracking in (0/90) Kevlar laminates, although

some work on the fatigue of Kevlar composites has been reported, e.g. [14-16]. In this study, data are presented from quasi-static and fatigue tests on KFRP laminates and the results compared with the analyses of Garrett and Bailey, and of Steif [1,17]. It is shown that there is a stiffening effect in the 0° plies of KFRP, peculiar to Kevlar fibres, which counteracts the modulus degradation due to matrix cracking, and complicates the application of these analyses.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Materials and specimen design.

Unidirectional (0°) coupons, 205mm by 25mm of Kevlar 49 fibre in epoxy resin were cut from unidirectional laminate. Similar test-pieces were machined from (0/90_n)s laminates ($n=1,2$). In all cases the 0° fibres were parallel to the length of the sample.

Quasi-Static Tests.

In the quasi-static tests, samples were loaded up to progressively higher stress levels using a screw driven Instron tensile testing machine. The Young's modulus was calculated on each load-up from the initial slope of the stress-strain curve. After reaching the required stress, the sample was unloaded to approximately 100 MPa. A photograph of the resulting array of parallel cracks was then taken with an SLR camera using a strong transmitted light source. The average transverse ply crack spacing, $2s$ was determined from the resulting photographic prints, and the average crack density, $1/2s$ was calculated.

Fatigue Tests.

Fatigue tests on the Kevlar 49/epoxy laminates were performed using a servo-hydraulic Instron 1271 machine at a frequency of 10 Hz. The coupons were tested over a range of maximum stress values, keeping the R value (minimum stress/maximum stress) constant at 0.1 throughout the tests. The Young's Modulus of the composite was recorded at regular intervals using a 70mm clip gauge on the sample and an Orion/Apple Datalogging system [18]. Plots of Modulus (E) and Normalised Modulus (E/E₀) against cycle number were constructed.

RESULTS.**Quasi-Static Tests on Unidirectional Laminates.**

The results for two different thicknesses of unidirectional composite (2 ply and 16 ply) are shown in Figure 1.

For the thin, 2 ply laminate the modulus appeared to be independent of applied stress up to approximately 400 MPa ($\approx 0.4\sigma_{UTS}$), when the modulus began to fall as a result of longitudinal splitting and delamination. The stiffness continued to drop as the stress increased, until multiple fibre breaks initiated final, catastrophic failure at 950 MPa. For the thick, 16 ply laminate, a different behaviour was observed. From the first load-up, the laminate exhibited an increase in modulus with applied stress, and this behaviour continued until about 600 MPa ($\approx 0.6\sigma_{UTS}$) when splitting and delamination caused the modulus to fall. Final failure also occurred at 950 MPa.

Figure 1. Normalised modulus as a function of applied stress for unidirectional KFRP laminates.

Recent experiments have shown that these modulus changes are solely a function of applied stress, and independent of strain rate.

Although this phenomenon in KFRP does not appear to be reported in the literature, it has been observed with Kevlar fibres themselves [19,20]. In these experiments [19], bundles of Kevlar fibres were subjected to 10 cycles of low frequency fatigue loading. The modulus was found to increase

with each cycle, with the rate of increase falling with number of cycles. For Kevlar 49 (Du Pont's high modulus fibre), this modulus increase was reversible— when the fibres were left to relax for 92 hours, and then retested, the modulus reverted to its original value. However, for Kevlar 29 (the high strength, low modulus fibre), the increase was semi-permanent, and although the modulus fell when the fibres were allowed to relax after the test, the stiffness did not drop back as far as its original value.

It has been suggested [19,20] that this increasing stiffness may be due to a re-alignment of both the fibres within a bundle, and the molecular chains within individual fibres. In Kevlar 49 this re-alignment is reversible , but in Kevlar 29 it results in a permanent modulus increase and an associated permanent strain as well.

An additional problem with laminates, as opposed to individual fibres and fibre bundles, is that there are large residual thermal stresses associated with Kevlar fibres embedded in epoxy. The fibres are held in longitudinal compression when the composite cools down from cure temperature as a result of the difference in thermal expansion coefficient of the two materials. This stress has been shown [19] to be sufficient in some cases to initiate the characteristic Kevlar V-bands, or kinks in the fibre, generally only observed above approximately 3% strain in compression tests on the fibres alone [21]. It may be that these kink bands are straightened out when an external stress is applied to the composite, and that in conjunction with better alignment of the fibrillar structure, the modulus increases.

It is possible that it is this molecular orientation that is causing the increase in modulus for the 16 ply samples shown in Fig.1. It may be that for the 2 ply samples, there is sufficient time between tests to allow the modulus to revert to its original value. For the 16 ply samples, there is insufficient time between tests, and the modulus increases. Indeed, when the samples are left to relax at zero load for a greater time between readings, the modulus began to drop back down to its original value.

These results seem to indicate that there is a temporary increase in strain which is dissipated by some time dependent behaviour when the unidirectional laminate is allowed sufficient time to relax at zero load. It may therefore be possible to model this behaviour by a 'spring and dashpot' arrangement.

Quasi-Static Tests on Cross-ply Laminates.

Plots of modulus change, (E/E_0) , against stress level for a number of tests on (0/90)s laminate all fall on the same general line (Figure 2). The overall modulus reduction of 5% was attributed to being solely due to the matrix cracking of the 90° plies. First cracking occurred at around 200 MPa (0.7% ϵ) with 'saturation' cracking being reached at around 450 MPa (1.3% ϵ). Catastrophic failure due to splitting, delamination and fibre breakage in the 0° plies occurred at around 600MPa.

The magnitude of the modulus reduction is approaching the value of 6% predicted by the ply discount scheme [22] (the ply discount scheme assumes that the cracked 90° plies offer no contribution to the stiffness of the laminate). This implies that any stiffening that may have occurred in the 0° plies was dissipated before the modulus reading was taken, as was the case previously for the unidirectional 2 ply sample.

The cracks in the 90° ply appeared to extend right across the width of the laminate from one free edge to the other, forming a fairly evenly

spaced ladder-like pattern. This pattern is very similar to that seen in CFRP under static loading by authors using dye-penetrant enhanced radiography, e.g.[4,23].

Figure 2. Normalised modulus as a function of applied stress for (0/90)_s KFRP laminates.

Figure 3. Experimental and theoretical modulus reduction with average crack density for quasi-static tests on cross-ply KFRP laminates.

Figure 3 shows a plot of modulus change against crack density for both the (0/90)_s and the (0/90)_{2s} KFRP laminates. The theoretical curves of modulus reduction with crack density using shear lag analyses [1,17] are also shown. For each laminate the lower of the two theoretical curves assumes a constant longitudinal displacement through the 90° ply, whilst the upper curve assumes a parabolic variation of longitudinal displacement. The data appear to fall between the two curves reasonably well.

Fatigue Tests on Unidirectional Laminates.

The cyclic loading of unidirectional composites resulted in significant increases in modulus (10% after 10^6 cycles). Morgan et al [24] suggest that there is some evidence for stiffening of this magnitude in Kevlar/epoxy laminates in fatigue, due to fibre alignment. Plotting the modulus against the number of cycles on a log scale (Figure 4) gives a straight line which would fit a power law dependency. It also appears that the rate of stiffening depends on stress level, with higher rates at higher stress levels, but more tests need to be conducted to establish this relationship.

Figure 4. Modulus with cycles for unidirectional 0° 2 ply KFRP laminate, at $\sigma_{max} = 640$ MPa (approx. $0.6\sigma_{UTS}$) and $\sigma_{max} = 320$ MPa (approx. $0.3\sigma_{UTS}$).

Fatigue Tests on Cross-ply laminates.

A plot is shown in Figure 5 for a fatigue test on a $(0/90_2)_s$ laminate at a maximum cyclic stress of 100 MPa, below the onset of static transverse ply cracking, where an overall increase of some 5% in the composite modulus was recorded. There were four distinct stages in the fatigue life. For the first 20 000 cycles, the modulus increased steadily; presumably as a result of the stiffening effect of the 0° plies. Between 20 000 and 50 000 cycles, cracks began to grow in the 90° ply, and this matrix cracking outweighed the 0° stiffening effect resulting in an overall drop in modulus. Once saturation cracking was reached, at around 10^6 cycles, the stiffening effect became dominant again, and the modulus began to increase once more. Towards the end of the fatigue life (2.5×10^6 cycles), other damage—delamination, splitting and 0° fibre breakages—occurred, resulting in a reduction in stiffness and eventually final failure.

Figure 5. Typical curve of modulus change with cycles for a (0/90₂)_s KFRP laminate.

The first three stages of this behaviour are shown more clearly by plotting the number of cycles on a log scale, as in Figure 6. In this way, the first few decades of cycles, which were concentrated by the modulus axis in Figure 5, are more easily read.

Figure 6 shows the fatigue test results for a number of different lay-ups at approximately the same maximum stress level, so that they can be compared directly. The two cross-ply laminates exhibited similar behaviour, with the matrix cracking having a greater influence on the resultant modulus in the samples with thicker transverse plies. It is apparent that Young's Modulus is not a particularly good damage parameter for KFRP, especially in fatigue loading. It may be that a different measure of stiffness, such as the principal Poisson's ratio, [22] may prove more useful, and perhaps decrease continuously with fatigue cycling.

In fatigue, the cracks formed a different pattern to that under static loading, especially at low applied stresses. Initially there were some transverse ply cracks which extended over the whole width of the specimen, but subsequent cracks appeared to progress by slow crack growth. The majority of these were initiated at and grew from the edges of the laminate, but there were also some cracks growing from the central section out towards the edges. Similar cracks growing from the centre have been observed in GFRP, but the situation in CFRP is uncertain due to the opaque nature of the material. Schematic pictures taken from photographic prints showing the crack pattern in static and fatigue loading are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Modulus change with cycles for (0/90 n)_s KFRP laminate, ($n=0,1,2$). All tests conducted at $0.3 \sigma_{UTS}$.

Figure 7. Transverse ply crack patterns for (0/90)_s KFRP laminate under A)Static and B)Fatigue loading.

CONCLUSIONS

In static and cyclic loading of cross-ply KFRP laminates, the changes in Young's Modulus are governed by two competing mechanisms. Re-orientation of the fibres and molecular chains in the 0° plies gives an increase in the composite modulus, whilst matrix cracking in the 90° plies tends to result in modulus degradation. The application of normalised modulus as a damage parameter for (0/90)_s KFRP laminate is therefore complicated, particularly under fatigue loading.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We wish to thank Dr. Will Smith and others at the E.I. Du Pont de Nemours Company, Wilmington, Delaware, U.S.A., for many helpful discussions, and for supplying the material. This work is made possible by the generous financial support of the Du Pont Company.

REFERENCES

1. Garrett,K.W., Bailey,J.E., Multiple transverse fracture in 90° cross ply laminates of a glass fibre reinforced polyester. J.Mater.Sci., 1977, 12, 157-68.
2. Garrett,K.W., Bailey,J.E., The effect of resin failure strain on the tensile properties of glass fibre reinforced polyester cross ply laminates. J.Mater.Sci., 1977, 12, 2189-94.
3. Bailey,J.E., Curtis,P.T., Parvizi,A., On the transverse cracking and longitudinal splitting behaviour of glass and carbon fibre reinforced epoxy cross-ply laminates and the effect of Poisson and thermally generated strain. Proc.Roy.Soc., London., 1979, A366, 599-623.
4. Masters,J.E., Reifsnider,K.L., An investigation of cumulative damage development in quasi-isotropic graphite/epoxy laminates. In Damage in Composite Materials, ed.K.L.Reifsnider, ASTM STP 775,1982, 40-62.
5. Reifsnider,K.L, Damage mechanisms in fatigue of composite materials. In Proc 3rd. Risø International Symposium on Metallurgy and Materials Science, eds. H.Lilholt & R.Talreja. Risø National Laboratory, Roskilde, Denmark.1982, 125-136.
6. Hahn,H.T., Tsai,S.W., On the behaviour of composite laminates after initial failures. J. Composite Mater., 1974 8, 288-305.
7. Wang,A.S.D., Growth mechanisms of transverse cracks and ply delaminations in composite laminates. In Proc. 3rd International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM 3), Paris, 1980, ed. A.Bunsell, Pergamon Press, 170-85.
8. Poursartip,A., Aspects of damage growth in fatigue of composites. PhD.Thesis, Department of Engineering,University of Cambridge. 1983.
9. Wang,A.S.D., Chou,P.C., Lei,S.C., A stochastic model for the growth of matrix cracks in composite laminates. J.Composite Mater. 1984, 18, 239-54.
- 10.Fukunaga,H, Chou,T-W., Peters,P.W.M., Schulte,K, Probabilistic failure strength analyses of graphite/epoxy cross ply laminates. J.Composite Mater., 1984, 18, 339-56.
- 11.Ogin,S.L., Smith,P.A., Beaumont,P.W.R., Matrix cracking and stiffness reduction during the fatigue of a (0/90)s GFRP laminate. Composites Science & Technology, 1985, 22, 23-31.
- 12.Ogin,S.L., Smith,P.A., Beaumont,P.W.R., A stress intensity factor approach to the fatigue growth of transverse ply cracks. Composites Science & Technology, 1985 24, 47-59.
- 13.Talreja,R., Transverse cracking and stiffness reduction in composite laminates. J.Composite Mater., 1985, 19, 355-75.

14. Hahn, H.T., Fatigue of composites: Environmental effects. In Proc. 3rd Risø international Symposium on Metallurgy & Materials Science. eds. H.Lilholt & R.Talreja. Risø National Laboratory, Roskilde, Denmark. 1982, 19-35.
15. Davidovitz, M., Mittleman, A., Roman, I., Marom, G., Failure modes and fracture mechanisms in flexure of Kevlar-epoxy composites. J.Mater.Sci., 1984, 19, 377-84.
16. Jones, C.J., Dickson, R.F., Adam, T., Reiter, H., Harris, B., The environmental fatigue behaviour of reinforced plastics. Proc.Roy.Soc., Lond. 1984, A396, 315-38.
17. Steif, P.S., Parabolic shear-lag analysis of a (0/90) laminate. Appendix to Cambridge University Engineering Department^s Technical Report CUED/C/MATS/TR.105, 1984.
18. Poursartip, A., Smith, P.A., Ganczakowski, H.L., Beaumont, P.W.R., A Computer Controlled Fatigue Machine For Composites Testing. Cambridge University Engineering Department Technical Report CUED/C/MATS/TR.132, 1986.
19. Smith, W., Riewald, P., E.I.Du Pont de Nemours Company, Wilmington, Delaware. Private Communication.
20. Bunsell, A. The tensile and fatigue behaviour of Kevlar 49 (PRD-49) fibre. J.Mater.Sci., 1975, 10, 1300-1308.
21. Deteresa, S.J., Allen, S.R., Farris, R.J., Porter, R.S., Compressive and torsional behaviour of Kevlar 49 fibre. J.Mater.Sci., 1984, 19, 57-72.
22. Highsmith, A.L., Reifsnider, K.L., Stiffness reduction mechanisms in composite laminates. In Damage in Composite Materials, ed. K.L.Reifsnider ASTM STP 775, 1982, 103-117.
23. Bader, M.G., Boniface, L., Damage development during quasi static and cyclic loading in GRP and CFRP laminates containing 90° plies. In Proc. Fifth International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-V), San Diego, 1985, 221-32.
24. Morgan, R.J., Mones, E.T., Steele, W.J., Deutscher, S.B., The failure modes and durability of Kevlar/epoxy composites. In Proc. 12th National SAMPE Conference, Seattle, Washington, 1980.